

ECONOMIC NATURE OF PRIVATE INVESTMENTS

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Private investment plays an important role in stimulating economic growth and innovation. It provides capital to emerging businesses, supports expansion plans and supports entrepreneurial initiatives. Private investments are made in companies, funds and assets that are not traded on the stock exchange, allowing investors to diversify their portfolios and earn higher returns. While private equity investments can offer rewarding opportunities, it is important to understand the underlying risks and complexities. Investors should carefully assess their risk tolerance, conduct due diligence and seek professional advice when entering this industry.

Private equity refers to the act of placing capital in companies, funds or assets that are not traded on the stock exchange. Unlike public investment, which involves buying and selling shares of publicly traded companies, private investment involves direct investment in private businesses or alternative investment vehicles. Private equity investments are typically made by high net worth individuals, institutional investors, venture capital firms, private equity firms, and angel investors. These investors provide capital to support the growth, expansion and development of private companies or innovative projects that have not yet gone public. Private equity investments can take many forms, including equity investments, debt investments, convertible securities, and stock investments. Equity investing involves the purchase of shares or ownership interests in a private company, giving the investor a proportional ownership stake and the potential for capital appreciation. Debt investment, on the other hand, involves lending money to a private company or project in exchange for regular interest payments and repayment of principal over time.

Convertible securities are a hybrid form of investment that can be converted into shares at a later stage. This allows investors to benefit from the safety and equity potential of debt instruments. Fund investing involves pooling the capital of several investors into a managed investment vehicle, such as a private equity fund or venture capital fund, which is then deployed in various private investment opportunities [1].

The main features of private investments

Private investment presents a unique set of characteristics that distinguish it from public investment. Let's look at the main features that make private investments unique:

Limited liquidity, high potential returns, access to unique investment opportunities, lower regulatory requirements, risk and lack of diversification. Types of private investments

Private equity includes a wide range of investment opportunities across a variety of sectors and asset classes. Let's take a look at some common types of private equity investments that investors can consider:

Private capital, venture capital, real estate infrastructure, debt instruments [2].

год	частные инвестиции, млрд. долл.	частные инвестиции на душу населения, долларов	частные инвестиции, млрд. долл.	рост частных инвестиций, %	доля частных инвестиций в ВВП, %	доля Узбекистана, %		
						текущие цены	постоянные цены 1990	в мире
1990	5.9	288.4	5.9		33.6	0.10	0.33	27.1
1991	5.1	241.6	4.9	-17.0	28.0	0.084	0.26	37.8
1992	7.6	350.6	7.2	45.4	45.8	0.12	0.35	44.5
1993	2.5	114.1	2.3	-67.5	15.3	0.040	0.11	27.4
1994	3.1	135.3	2.8	18.6	19.1	0.044	0.12	28.0
1995	4.1	177.8	3.6	31.3	25.3	0.053	0.14	40.2
1996	4.0	171.7	3.9	7.0	24.0	0.052	0.14	43.5
1997	3.7	154.5	4.5	17.0	19.8	0.048	0.14	41.1
1998	3.9	161.8	4.7	4.6	21.8	0.052	0.17	42.9
1999	3.7	148.9	4.8	1.1	17.9	0.047	0.15	42.7
2000	3.4	135.5	4.8	0.90	20.4	0.041	0.12	38.4
2001	2.3	92.5	5.0	4.0	21.1	0.029	0.093	21.5
2002	2.5	96.8	5.2	3.6	21.1	0.031	0.099	20.7
2003	2.4	93.9	5.5	4.5	20.2	0.027	0.085	17.9
2004	3.5	133.0	5.7	4.9	24.3	0.033	0.10	19.1
2005	4.5	170.1	6.1	7.0	26.5	0.039	0.12	17.3
2006	5.9	220.9	6.5	6.5	28.5	0.046	0.15	15.8
2007	7.5	276.3	8.3	27.3	27.7	0.051	0.16	15.0
2008	11.7	421.5	10.9	31.9	32.0	0.072	0.20	20.1
2009	12.7	451.8	13.9	27.4	30.1	0.090	0.22	21.7
2010	13.6	475.1	15.7	12.6	27.2	0.083	0.20	20.7
2011	16.2	556.1	16.6	5.7	26.7	0.086	0.20	20.4
2012	20.4	692.3	20.0	20.6	30.1	0.11	0.23	21.8
2013	20.1	670.9	19.6	-2.0	27.5	0.10	0.22	19.5
2014	22.6	742.3	21.3	8.8	28.0	0.11	0.24	21.0
2015	22.7	733.7	21.5	1.0	26.3	0.12	0.25	23.2
2016	22.2	705.5	22.3	3.6	25.8	0.11	0.24	26.6
2017	18.1	566.1	26.3	18.1	29.1	0.085	0.18	20.8
2018	19.7	606.1	35.6	35.2	37.2	0.086	0.17	21.4
2019	25.2	764.3	42.4	19.1	41.8	0.11	0.22	24.2
2020	24.1	717.6	41.3	-2.5	40.0	0.11	0.21	23.8
2021	28.1	824.3	44.9	8.5	40.4	0.11	0.21	24.7
2022	30.8	889.3	38.4	-14.5	38.3	0.11	0.23	23.9

Figure 1. Volume of private investment in 1990-2022 [3].

For 1990-2001. Private investments per capita in Uzbekistan decreased by 195.9 dollars (67.9 percent) and amounted to 92.5 dollars. The average annual growth of private investment per capita was -17.8 dollars or -9.8% at current prices. During 2001-2022, private investments per capita in Uzbekistan increased by 796.8 dollars (9.6 times) and amounted to 889.3 dollars. The average annual growth of private investment per capita at current prices was 37.9 dollars or 11.4 percent.

In short, Private Equity gives investors access to unique investment opportunities, potentially higher returns, and a more active role in their

portfolios. By conducting private investment due diligence and seeking professional guidance, individuals and institutions can navigate this exciting area of finance and manage the performance of their investment efforts.

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